

THE EFFECT OF HEAT-TREATMENT ON THE ADSORPTION BEHAVIOR OF SILANE COUPLING AGENT

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ABSTRACT

The adsorption characteristics of the silane onto the silica surface were investigated by using GPC, elemental analysis and CP/MAS ²⁹Si NMR. The characteristics of the silane chemisorbed onto the silica surface are changed by the heat-treatment temperature. When the silica with deposited silane was heat-treated below 80 °C, the mono-layer of the chemisorbed silane is formed on the surface. However, when the silica with deposited silane was heat-treated at 110 °C, the multi-layer of the chemisorbed silane is formed on the surface. Further, excess amounts of the silane species exist on the chemisorbed layer as a physisorbed layer.

The hydrolytic durability of the silane bi-layer, that is comprised of the chemisorbed mono-layer and physisorbed layer, is higher than the silane bi-layer, that is comprised of the chemisorbed multi-layer and physisorbed layer. When the silica with deposited silane was heat-treated below 80 °C, most of the chemisorbed silane molecules have silanol groups, which can form hydrogen bonds with the silanol groups of the physisorbed silane molecules. However, when the silica with deposited silane was heat-treated at 110 °C, the chemisorbed silane molecules, which have no silanol group, increases. This indicates that the physisorbed silane is more loosely associated by weaker Van der Waals attractions to the chemisorbed silane molecules rather than by hydrogen bonding. Increased hydrolytic stability is provided by the molecules which have an increased potential for hydrogen bonding.

INTRODUCTION

The fact that the fiber/matrix interface controls the mechanical properties of polymeric composite materials is well understood. The characteristics of the fiber/matrix interface that is comprised of silane coupling agents are affected by the adsorption properties and the degree of the adsorption of the silane¹⁻⁵). In order to gain a fundamental understanding of the reinforcement properties of the polymeric composites, it is essential to determine the parameters and characteristics of these interfaces.

The purpose of this study was to determine and investigate the effects of heat-treatment on silica with deposited silane by utilizing elemental analysis, gel permeation chromatography, GPC, and cross-polarization/magic-angle spinning silicone ²⁹ Nuclear magnetic resonance, CP/MAS ²⁹Si NMR, and to investigate the adsorption characteristics of silane molecules on the silica surface.

Further, in order to understand which parameters control the hydrolytic stability of the silane bi-layer that is comprised of chemisorbed silane and physisorbed silane at the silica/matrix interface, the characteristics of the silane molecules that are adsorbed onto the surface were investigated by correlating it with the hydrolytic stability of the fiber/matrix interface by a tensile test.

On the basis of this concept, the relationship between the hydrolytic durability and the adsorption behavior is discussed.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

1. Materials

γ -methacryloxypropyltrimethoxysilane (γ -MPS) from Shinetsu Silicone was used as received. The spherical silica particle (SO-25R) from Tatsumori was also used as received. The surface area of the silica and the number of the Si-OH groups on the silica surface were determined to be 10.01 m²/g, BET, and 4.73/nm², respectively.

2. Silane treatment

0.30 g of the silane, γ -MPS, was dissolved in 10 ml of water (the water was deionized and has a pH of 6.4) - ethanol solution. The silane was allowed to hydrolyze in the silane solution for one hour. After hydrolysis, 10.0 g of the silica were added to the silane solution. The silica was then air-dried at 25 °C. After one day, the silica with deposited silane was heat-treated at 50, 80, or 110 °C for 3 hours.

3. GPC measurement

After the silica with deposited silane was heat-treated at different temperatures, the silane physisorbed onto the silica surface was removed by dispersing the silane-treated silica into tetrahydrofuran (THF) for 2 hours. After stirring, the suspension was centrifuged. The supernatant solution was then injected into GPC (LC-6A, Shimadzu). The UV detector (SBD-6AV, Shimadzu) was used at a wave length of 235 nm.

4. Elemental analysis

The silane-treated silica was dispersed into THF, and then the suspension was stirred for 2 hours. After the suspension was centrifuged, the supernatant solution was discarded. Again, the silica was dispersed into THF. The same procedures were repeated as described above in order to completely remove the physisorbed silane. This was repeatedly continued until it was impossible to observe the silane in the supernatant solution that was used for GPC analysis. The amount of chemisorbed silane onto the silica surface was determined from the amount of carbon by using elemental analysis (MT 3 type, Yanagimoto). In addition, the total amount of deposited silane on the silica surface was determined by using elemental analysis.

5. CP/MAS ²⁹Si NMR observation

After the silane-treated silica was repeatedly rinsed with THF in order to completely remove the physisorbed silane, the solid state CP/MAS ²⁹Si NMR spectra were observed by using JEOL 270 at 53.54 MHz. This was performed to obtain information concerning the characteristics of the silane molecule chemisorbed onto the silica surface. The magic-angle sample spinning was carried out at 4.5 KHz spinning rates. The spectra were obtained by using a contact time of 10 msec, a pulse repetition time of 1.0 second, accumulation, 16,000 scans.

6. Hydrolytic stability of the silane at the silica/matrix interface

The procedures to prepare the specimen for the tensile test are shown in Fig. 1. The silica plate was treated with the silane by using 70 % ethanol solution as mentioned above, and the concentration of the silane was 5x10⁻² mol/l. Thus the silica plate was immersed in the silane solution for 2 hours after the silane was hydrolyzed in a silane solution for one hour. Then the silica plate was removed, and completely air-dried at 25 °C. After one day, the silica plate with deposited silane was heat-treated at 50, 80, or 110 °C for 3 hours. Then the silicone ring mold, with an internal diameter of 3.2 mm and a depth of 2.0 mm, was attached to the silane-treated silica plate by using sticky wax. Then the dental composite resin (Clearfil F-II, Kuraray, Redox cured type, benzoyl peroxide-tertiary amine system) was filled into the inside of the ring mold. The composite resin was cured at 37 °C for one day. At this point, the resin was adhered to the silica surface by the silane bi-layer. Then the specimen was immersed in

Fig.1 Schematic diagram specimen for tensile bond strength.

a : silicone ring, b : brass cap attachment

boiling water by using Soxhlet's extractor for 0, 100, 200, 300, and 400 hours. After degradation, the specimen was positioned on the tensile testing machine (Shinko, TCM-500CR). The tensile strength of the resin with the silane-treated silica plate was measured under a cross-head speed of 2.0 mm/min. The number of specimens for each experiment was 20.

RESULTS

1. Effect of water content in silane solution on adsorption behavior of silane molecules onto silica surface

Fig. 2 shows the amount of adsorbed silane onto the silica surface by changing the water content in the silane solution comprised of water and ethanol. The silica with deposited silane was dried at 25 °C for one day. The mark "○" shows the total amount of deposited silane on the surface, and "●" shows the amount of chemisorbed silane. In this experiment, the amount of adsorbed silane onto the surface was determined by assuming the adsorbed silane molecules are the triol of the γ -MPS monomer. Because 10.0 g of the silica was treated with 0.30 g of the silane, the theoretical amount of adsorbed silane onto the surface was approximately 24.9 mg/g.

When the water content in the silane solution was 5 vol%, the total amount of deposited silane on the surface was 26.5 mg/g. By increasing the water content in the silane solution, the total amount of deposited silane decreased. When the water content was 40 vol%, the total amount of deposited silane, 22.3 mg/g, became smaller than the theoretical value, 24.9 mg/g. This is due to the intermolecular condensation of the hydrolyzed silane molecules as shown in Fig. 3. Further, when the water content was under 10 vol%, the complete unhydrolyzed silane molecules, such as tri-, di- and mono-methoxysilane, existed on the silica surface. Because the amount of adsorbed silane was determined by the amount of carbon, the total amount of deposited silane was larger than the theoretical value, 24.9 mg/g.

In contrast, the amount of the chemisorbed silane onto the surface increased from 3.7 mg/g to 8.6 mg/g, until the water content in the silane solution reached 30 vol%. This was due to the fact that the chemisorption of the silane molecules was limited by the production of the hydrolyzed silane molecules. However, the amount of chemisorbed silane leveled off, even though the water content was increased from 30 vol% to 40 vol%. At this point, the chemisorbed layer became saturated, and the mono-layer of the chemisorbed silane is formed on the silica surface. The saturated amount of chemisorbed silane was 9 mg/g. As a result, excess amounts of the silane molecules were occluded on the chemisorbed layer which was formed on the silica surface as a physisorbed silane and was associated by hydrogen bonding and Van der Waals attractions³⁻⁶.

In our previous papers¹⁻³), the amount of the chemisorbed silane, γ -MPS, onto the silica surface was investigated as a result of the concentration of γ -MPS, when the silica with

Fig.2 Amount of silane on silica surface as a function of concentration of water in silane solution.

Fig.3 GPC chromatograms of physisorbed silane on silica surface as a function of concentration of water in silane solution. M : monomer, D : dimer, T : tetramer

deposited silane was dried at room temperature (25°C). The saturated amount of chemisorbed silane onto the surface is approximately 100 mg/g. The surface area of the silica, 10.01 m²/g used in this experiment, is approximately 1/13 of the surface area of the colloidal silica, 130 m²/g. On the basis of the ratio of the surface area, the amount of chemisorbed silane was calculated. The chemisorbed amount of silane on the surface was determined to be 7.7 mg/g by assuming that the chemisorbed amount of silane is dependent on the surface area of the silica. This calculated value, 7.7 mg/g, approximately agrees with the amount of chemisorbed silane, approximately 8.6 mg/g, obtained in this experiment.

Further, the molecular weight of the physisorbed silane molecules, which was extracted from the surface, increased by increasing the water content in the silane solution as shown in Fig. 3. This was due to the intermolecular condensation of the hydrolyzed silane molecules. When the water content in the silane solution was above 30 vol%, tetramer was produced. This was attributed to the fact that the degree and rate of the hydrolysis of the methoxy group in the silane molecule is limited by the amount of water in the silane solution⁷⁾.

2. Effect of heat-treatment temperature on adsorption behavior of silane molecules onto silica surface

Fig. 4 shows the amount of adsorbed silane onto the silica surface by changing the heat-treatment temperatures. The 70 vol% ethanol solution was used for silane treatment. After the silica was dried at 25 °C for one day, the silica with deposited silane was heat-treated at 50, 80, or 110 °C. The mark "○" shows the total amount of deposited silane on the surface, and "●" shows the amount of chemisorbed silane.

When the silica with deposited silane was dried at 25 °C, the total amount of deposited silane on the surface was 24.6 mg/g. By raising the heat-treatment temperature, the total amount of deposited silane decreased. When the heat-treatment temperature was 110 °C, the total amount of deposited silane became 20.7 mg/g. This is attributed to the fact that the intermolecular condensation of the hydrolyzed silane molecules was accelerated by increasing the heat-treatment temperature as shown in Fig. 5.

In contrast, the amount of the chemisorbed silane onto the surface was constant at approximately 8.4-9.6 mg/g, until the heat-treatment temperature reached 80 °C. This was due to the fact that the mono-layer of the chemisorbed silane was formed on the silica surface as described above (Fig. 2). Therefore, excess amounts of the silane molecules were physisorbed onto the mono-layer of the chemisorbed silane formed on the silica surface. However, when the silica with the deposited silane was heat-treated at 110 °C, the amount of chemisorbed silane dramatically increased from 8.4 mg/g to 20.0 mg/g, indicating the formation of the silane multi-layer. This is attributed to the fact that the physisorbed silane molecules of the higher molecular

Fig.4 Amount of silane on silica surface as a function of heat-treatment temperature.

Fig.5 GPC chromatograms of physisorbed silane on silica surface as a function of heat-treatment temperature.

M : monomer, D : dimer, T : tetramer

Fig.6 CP/MAS ^{29}Si -NMR spectra of silica before and after silane treatment.

(1) : nontreated silica, (2) : silane-treated silica at 25°C

weight was forcefully condensed on the chemisorbed silane molecules which formed the monolayer on the surface. As a result, the peak attributed to the silane molecules of the higher molecular weight, such as tetramer, disappeared, indicating chemisorption. The peaks of the molecular species attributed to the monomer and dimer molecules were only observed in the GPC chromatogram (Fig. 5).

Figs. 6 and 7 demonstrate the CP/MAS ^{29}Si NMR spectra of the silane molecules that were chemisorbed onto the silica surface. The ^{29}Si peak assignment^{5,8)} is summarized in Table 1.

Fig. 6 shows the ^{29}Si NMR spectra of the silica before and after silane treatment. The 70 vol% ethanol solution was used for silane treatment. After the silica with deposited silane was dried at 25 °C, the silane-treated silica was repeatedly rinsed with THF to completely remove the physisorbed silane. The spectrum (1) is for nontreated silica, (2) is for the silane-treated silica at 25 °C. The change of the relative intensity of the peaks "a" and "b", which are attributable to the Si atom of the silica, is observed before and after the silane treatment. This schematic indicates the formation of siloxane bond between the Si-OH group (peak "b") on the silica surface and $-\text{CH}_2-\text{Si}-\text{OH}$ group in the silane molecule. Thereby, leading to an increase of the peak "a" and a decrease of the peak "b".

Fig. 7 shows the effect of the heat-treatment temperature on the chemisorption characteristics of the chemisorbed silane. After the silica with deposited silane was heat-treated at different temperatures, the silane-treated silica was repeatedly rinsed with THF to completely remove the physisorbed silane. Each spectrum of the chemisorbed silane was obtained by subtracting the spectrum of the nontreated silica. The peaks "c", "d", and "e" are attributed to the Si atom in the silane molecules that were chemisorbed onto the silica surface (Table 1). When the silica with deposited silane was heat-treated, the relative peak intensity of the peak "e" increased by increasing the heat-treatment temperature. The silane molecules attributed to the peak "c" does not have the silanol groups to allow hydrogen bonding with the silanol groups of the physisorbed silane, indicating the formation of the chemically stable multi-layer of the chemisorbed silane by tri-siloxane bond. This means that the probability to form hydrogen bonds between silanol groups of the chemisorbed and the physisorbed silane molecules decreases. The characteristics of the chemisorbed silane are changed by the heat-treatment temperature. The chemisorption characteristics of the silane would affect the cohesive force of the silane bi-layer comprised of the chemisorbed layer and the physisorbed layer, which is supported by hydrogen bonding⁵⁾. This is due to the fact that the molecular species attributed to peaks "c" and "d" can form hydrogen bonds with the physisorbed silane molecules.

3. Effect of adsorption characteristics of silane molecules onto silica surface on hydrolytic durability of silane at silica/resin interface

Fig. 8 shows the contact angle of a waterdrop to the silane-treated silica surface by changing the heat-treatment temperature. The 70 vol% ethanol solution was used for silane treatment.

Fig.7 CP/MAS ^{29}Si NMR spectra of chemisorbed silane onto silica surface as a function of heat-treatment temperature.

After drying at 25 °C for one day, the silica plate was heat-treated at 50, 80, or 110 °C. The mark "○" shows before and "●" shows after rinsing of the silane-treated silica plate with THF. Before rinsing with THF, the contact angle of a waterdrop increased by increasing the heat-treatment temperature, reflecting the increase in the molecular weight of the physisorbed silane (Fig. 5) and the increase in the amount of chemisorbed silane (Fig. 4). However, when the silane-treated silica plate was rinsed with THF by using Soxhlet's extractor for 30 hours, reduction of the contact angle was observed, indicating the desorption of the physisorbed silane molecules⁶). The removable silane molecules exist on the chemisorbed silane layer. The silane bi-layer comprised of the chemisorbed layer and physisorbed layer was formed on the silica surface.

Next, the hydrolytic durability of the silane bi-layer comprised of the chemisorbed layer and physisorbed layer was examined by changing the heat-treatment temperature (Fig. 9). Before degradation, the tensile bond strength of the resin was approximately 15 MPa. The cohesive failure of the resin was observed under different heat-treatment conditions. However, when the specimen was immersed in boiling water, the bond strength of the resin decreased by increasing the immersion time (Fig. 9). The failure mechanism changes from cohesive failure to interfacial failure. This is due to the hydrolysis of the silane bi-layer at the silica/matrix interface. However, the degree of the reduction in the bond strength is dependent on the heat-treatment temperature. The immersion time to start the mixed failure of cohesive and interfacial failure was 200 hours below 80 °C and 100 hours at 110 °C, respectively. When the silica with deposited silane was heat-treated at 110 °C, the bond strength became 6.0 MPa after degradation for 100 hours.

Further, when the silica plate with deposited silane was dried at 25 °C, the bond strength of the resin was 8.4 MPa even though the specimen was immersed in boiling water for 400 hours. However, the bond strength was 7.0 MPa at 50 °C and 6.2 MPa at 80 °C after degradation for 400 hours. The bond strength gradually decreases by increasing the heat-treatment temperature. The reduction rate of the bond strength increases by increasing the heat-treatment temperature. The hydrolytic stability of the silane bi-layer is strongly dependent on the adsorption characteristics of the silane molecules. This is due to the fact that the molecular weight of the physisorbed silane become higher (Fig. 5). This is attributed to the fact that the silanol group of the physisorbed silane molecules, which can form hydrogen bonds with the silanol group of the chemisorbed silane molecules, decreases by increasing the molecular weight of the physisorbed silane. The cohesive force is influenced by the characteristics of the chemisorbed and physisorbed silane molecules.

Fig. 8 Contact angle of a waterdrop to silane-treated silica surface as a function of heat-treatment temperature.

Fig. 9 Tensile bond strength of resin with silane-treated silica surface as a function of immersion time.

○, △, □, ◇ : cohesive failure
 ◐, ◑, ◒, ◓ : mixed failure
 ●, ▲, ■, ◆ : interfacial failure

DISCUSSIONS

In order to obtain information concerning the hydrolytic durability of the silane bi-layer at the silica/matrix interface, the adsorption characteristics of the silane onto the silica surface were investigated by using GPC, elemental analysis and CP/MAS ²⁹Si NMR (Figs 2-7). The characteristics of the silane chemisorbed on the silica surface are changed by the heat-treatment temperature (Fig. 7). This is due to the amount of chemisorbed silane on the silica surface (Fig. 4). When the silica with deposited silane was heat-treated below 80 °C, the mono-layer of the chemisorbed silane was formed on the surface. However, when the silica with deposited silane was heat-treated at 110 °C, the multi-layer of the chemisorbed silane was formed on the surface. Further, excess amounts of deposited silane exist on the chemisorbed layer as a physisorbed layer (Figs. 4 and 5). The silane bi-layer that is comprised of the chemisorbed layer and physisorbed layer is formed on the silica surface.

In order to investigate the influence of the adsorption behavior of the silane molecules on the hydrolytic stability at the silica/matrix interface, the tensile bond strength of the methacrylic resin with the silane-treated silica was measured by a tensile test after the specimen was immersed in boiling water by using Soxhlet's extractor (Fig. 9). The hydrolytic stability of the silane bi-layer comprised of the chemisorbed mono-layer and physisorbed layer is higher than the silane bi-layer comprised of the chemisorbed multi-layer and physisorbed layer (Fig. 9). When the silica with deposited silane was heat-treated below 80 °C, most of the chemisorbed silane molecules have silanol groups which can form hydrogen bonds with the silanol groups of the physisorbed silane molecules. However, when the silica with deposited silane was heat-treated at 110 °C, the chemisorbed silane molecules which have no silanol group increase, indicating the decrease in the cohesive force of the silane bi-layer comprised of the chemisorbed layer and physisorbed layer. This is due to the fact that the cohesive force of the silane bi-layer is mostly supported by hydrogen bonding rather than by weaker Van der Waals attractions⁵. The increased hydrolytic stability is provided by the molecules which have an increased potential for hydrogen bonding.

Further, when the silica with deposited silane was heat-treated below 80 °C, the total amount of chemisorbed and physisorbed silane are quite similar (Fig. 4). The differences in the distribution of the molecular weight of the physisorbed silane molecules become apparent (Fig. 5). After degradation, the tensile bond strength of the methacrylic resin with the silane-treated silica was investigated by a tensile test (Fig. 9). The increase in the molecular weight of the

physisorbed silane hasten the degradation time of the silane bi-layer comprised of the chemisorbed mono-layer and physisorbed layer at the silica/matrix interface. This is due to the decrease in the silanol group of the physisorbed silane molecules, which can form hydrogen bonds with the silanol groups of the chemisorbed silane molecules on the surface. The increase of the molecular weight of the physisorbed silane molecules decreases the cohesive force of the silane bi-layer. This is due to the decreases of the probability to form hydrogen bonds between silanol groups of the chemisorbed and the physisorbed silane molecules. The hydrolytic durability of the silane bi-layer is strongly dependent upon the cohesive force between the chemisorbed and physisorbed layer, which is supported by hydrogen bonding.

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